

An Introduction To The Symbolic 3-Plithogenic Number Theory

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to study the foundations number theory in 3-plithogenic rings of integers, where concepts such as symbolic 3-plithogenic congruencies, division, and greatest common divisors.

Keywords: Symbolic 3-plithogenic integer, symbolic 3-plithogenic division, symbolic 3-plithogenic semi prime.

Introduction and basic concepts

The concept of symbolic plithogenic algebraic structures was defined by Smarandache [1-5], and it was studied for the special case of $n=2$ by many authors [6-11].

In this work, we concentrate on the case of symbolic 3-plithogenic number theory, we explain the some algorithms and basic concepts in a similar way of the 2-plithogenic case.

We will not write the proofs, that is because they are similar to the classical case, and can be found in [10].

For basic definitions of 2-symbolic plithogenic rings and algebraic operations see [6].

Main Discussion

Definition.

Let $A = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3, B = b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2 + b_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_Z$, we say that $A \setminus B$ if and only if there exists $C \in 3 - SP_Z$ such that $A \times B = C$.

Definition.

Let $A = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3, B = b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2 + b_3P_3, C = c_0 + c_1P_1 + c_2P_2 + c_3P_3$ be three symbolic 3-plithogenic integers, then $A \equiv B(mod C)$ if and only if $C \setminus A - B$.

Also, $C = gcd(A, B)$ if and only if $C \setminus A$ and $C \setminus B$ and for any $D \setminus A, D \setminus B$, then $D \setminus C$.

Definition.

We say that $A \leq B$ if $a_0 \leq b_0, a_0 + a_1 \leq b_0 + b_1, a_0 + a_1 + a_2 \leq b_0 + b_1 + b_2, a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3 \leq b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3$.

Theorem.

Let $A = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3, B = b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2 + b_3P_3, C = c_0 + c_1P_1 + c_2P_2 + c_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_Z$, then:

- 1). (\leq) is a partial order relation.
- 2). $A \setminus B$ if and only if $a_0 \setminus b_0, a_0 + a_1 \setminus b_0 + b_1, a_0 + a_1 + a_2 \setminus b_0 + b_1 + b_2, a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3 \setminus b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3$.
- 3). $gcd(A, B) = C$ if and only if $gcd(a_0, b_0) = c_0, gcd(a_0 + a_1, b_0 + b_1) = c_0 + c_1, gcd(a_0 + a_1 + a_2, b_0 + b_1 + b_2) = c_0 + c_1 + c_2, gcd(a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3, b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3) = c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3$.
- 4). $A \equiv B(mod C)$ if and only if:

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &\equiv b_0(mod c_0) \\ a_0 + a_1 &\equiv b_0 + b_1(mod c_0 + c_1) \\ a_0 + a_1 + a_2 &\equiv b_0 + b_1 + b_2(mod c_0 + c_1 + c_2) \\ a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3 &\equiv b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3(mod c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + c_3) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem.

Let $A = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3, B = b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2 + b_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_Z$, then $gcd(A, B) = 1$ if and only if $gcd(a_0, b_0) = 1, gcd(a_0 + a_1, b_0 + b_1) = 1, gcd(a_0 + a_1 + a_2, b_0 + b_1 + b_2) = 1, gcd(a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3, b_0 + b_1 + b_2 + b_3) = 1$.

Theorem.

Let $A, B, C, D, E \in 3 - SP_Z$, where:

$A = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3, B = b_0 + b_1P_1 + b_2P_2 + b_3P_3, C = c_0 + c_1P_1 + c_2P_2 + c_3P_3, D = d_0 + d_1P_1 + d_2P_2 + d_3P_3, E = e_0 + e_1P_1 + e_2P_2 + e_3P_3; c_i, a_i, b_i, e_i, d_i \in Z$, then:

- 1). If $A \equiv B(mod C), D \equiv E(mod C)$, then $A + D \equiv B + E(mod C), A - D \equiv B - E(mod C)$.
- 2). $A \cdot D \equiv B \cdot E(mod C)$.

All the proofs are similar to the case of 2-symbolic plithogenic case.

Definition.

Let $A = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3 > 0$ be a symbolic 3-plithogenic integer, we define $\varphi_S: 3 - SP_Z \rightarrow 3 - SP_Z$ such that:

$$\varphi_S(A) = \varphi(a_0) + P_1[\varphi(a_0 + a_1) - \varphi(a_0)] + P_2[\varphi(a_0 + a_1 + a_2) - \varphi(a_0 + a_1)] + P_3[\varphi(a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3) - \varphi(a_0 + a_1 + a_2)].$$

Where φ is the classical phi-Euler's function.

Theorem.

Let $A = a_0 + a_1P_1 + a_2P_2 + a_3P_3, M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2 + m_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_Z$ such that $gcd(A, M) = 1$, then

$$A^{\varphi_S(M)} \equiv 1(mod M).$$

Definition.

Let $S = s_0 + s_1P_1 + s_2P_2 + s_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_Z$, we say that S is a 3-plithogenic semi prime if $s_0, s_0 + s_1, s_0 + s_1 + s_2, s_0 + s_1 + s_2 + s_3$ are primes.

Example.

The 3-plithogenic integer $S = 2 + P_1 + 2P_2 + 2P_3$ is a semi prime, that is because $s_0 = 2, s_0 + s_1 = 3, s_0 + s_1 + s_2 = 5, s_0 + s_1 + s_2 + s_3 = 7$ are primes.

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